

Rathi – The Desert Rani

Dr. Amit Saraswat

Project coordinator, Rathi cattle pedigree selection program, Rashtriya Gokul Mission-NDDDB
Urmul Trust Bikaner

Corresponding Author: saraswatamit10@gmail.com

Rathi is a mosaic indigenous breed, believed to be evolved from Sahiwal, Tharparkar, Dhanni and Red Sindhi breeds. It is also known as “Desert Rani”. It is believed that the word “Rathi” was coined by the local people in Lunkaransar area of Rajasthan. The actual meaning of *Rathi* in *Marwar* language is ‘*very docile and calm animal*’. While some believes that Rathi name might have originated from a pastoral tribe called Raths who are muslims of

Rajput extraction and lead a nomadic life. Home tract of Rathi cattle is mainly Lunkaransar Tehsil of Bikaner district and some area of Ganganagar, Hanumangarh and Churu district of Rajasthan.

The Rathi is medium sized cattle with short horn or absent horn, straight face, flat forehead, wide eyes, well developed fore and hind quarter, long naval flap. The Rathi cattle are usually brown in color with white patches all over the body. Although some cattle are found to be completely brown or black coat with white patches. The typical characteristics of Rathi cattle is that it easily acclimatized with wide range of climatic condition like chilly winter (2⁰C) to hot summer (50⁰C) and even withstand sand-storm. On an average Rathi cattle produce 5-10 kg milk per day with lactation milk yield ranging from 1500-3000 Kg.

Recognizing the potential of Rathi breed, National Dairy Development Board (NDDDB) initiated Rathi breed conservation and development programme in Bikaner and Shri Ganganagar districts of Rajasthan since 2002. Under National Dairy Plant Phase-I (NDP-I), a pedigree selection project was implemented by NDDDB in the native tract of Rathi during 20112-2019 in association with URMUL trust for genetic improvement of Rathi cattle. The programme has been further continued under Rashtriya Gokul Mission (RGM) scheme of Department of Animal Husbandry and Dairying of GoI. The performance of Rathi cattle recorded at the farmers' herd during NDP-

is given in Table 1. The project was implemented in 120 villages of Lunkaransar and Chhatargarh Tehsils of Bikaner district. The physical progress of the project till Mar'2020 given in below table.

Table 1: Rathi PS Project: Breeding activity recorded in INAPH' till Mar 2020

Breeding activity						Nominated Inseminations		
No. of animal registered	No. of AIs	No. of PD done	No. of calving	No. of milk record	No. of animal's milk recorded	No. of Nominated AIs	No. of Cow Involved	No. of Bull Involved
67685	75916	59921	23852	34048	3955	1711	2,262	16

The project provided 31 High genetic merit (HGM) bull calves to Bull distribution committee, Govt. of India till Mar 2020 and many more are available in field under disease testing.

Figure 1: Rathi PS Project: Year Wise-Breeding activity recorded in INAPH' till Mar 2020

Figure 2: Rathi PS Project: Year wise-Conception Rate of AI recorded in INAPH’ till 2019

Figure 3: Rathi PS Project: Lactation curve of milk recorded in INAPH’ till Mar 2020

Table 2: Rathi PS Project: Top 5 AI technicians on basis of Conception Rate of AI recorded in INAPH’ till 2019

Rank	Name	AI	PD+VE	CR
1	Manphul Sidh	2407	1261	52.4
2	Rajendra Kumar	1393	721	51.8
3	Vikaram Yadav	1968	1005	51.1
4	Beant Singh	1571	788	50.2
5	Bhajan Lal Dudi	1763	884	50.1

Table 3: Rathi PS Project: Average Production and Reproduction trait

Particulars	No of observation in INAPH	Average Values
Age at first insemination (month)	194	31
Age at first calving (month)	52	41
Calving interval (month)	1327	14
Gestation Days (days)	16151	286
Service period (days)	694	148
Average Conception Rate	75916	43.2
Average 305-day Milk yield (Kg)	3965	2693
Fat %	2444	3.9
SNF %	2437	8.15

URMUL Rathi Pedigree selection project prides

Our pride: Farmer- Shri Ramkisan S/O Lunaram Jaat Shri Ramkisan is a resident of 3 RJD village of tehsil Chhatargarh of Bikaner district. He is a progressive and hardworking farmer. At present, He is maintaining a herd of 30 animals comprising of **Rathi** breed. Around 8-10 animals remain in milk throughout the year. Previously, they used to prefer natural service to get their animals pregnant but later on decided to participate in the pedigree selection project under NDP-I. Initially, he was reluctant to get his animal's ear tagged due to social taboo. But, after discussion with the project officials, he realized the benefit of AI and Unique identification of animal by ear tagging with 12 digit tag ID, agreed to register his animals in INAPH and even put his animals under milk recording. His change in attitude was an eye opener for other neighboring farmers later, one high genetic merit bull calf born through nominated AI was procured also.

Following the advice from the project officials, he started growing fodder crops to feed his animals. At present, he is selling around **70** Kg of milk per day directly to the private dairy and preparing ghee from milk at home. With the increasing demand for Rathi cattle in country, farmers from different states even approached him for Rathi cows and paid good price for his animals.

Now, Sh. Ramkisan along with his wife are leading a happy family life and they feel proud to be part of the project which has improved the socio-economic status of their family.

Our pride: AI Technician (AIT): Shri Bhagirath Kaswan S/O Hansraj Kaswan

Shri Bhagirath is working as AI technician with this project since last 18 years. He is a resident of Dheerdan village of Tehsil Lunkarnsar. Due to his poor financial situation, he could not able to continue his education after 10th standard during the year 1996. Then he started working with URMUL dairy as a milk collector. He associated with Rathi breed development project in 2002 and got trained for AI from NDDDB training center (Northern Regional Demonstration and Training Centre National Dairy Development Board, Jalandhar) in 2007. After completion of training, he started delivering AI services under the project from 2007 onwards. Currently he is continuing his work under PS RATHI RGM. Over the years, he has gained experience and competency. The year wise performance of Sh.Bhagirath is presented in adjacent graph.

He has also played a significant role in achieving HGM bull production target under the project.

His long association with project not only helped him to earn livelihood for himself and family but to earn respect within his society and villages.

His long association and contribution to the project is inspiration to other AIT. With his dedication, hard work in the project, he has become a role model for the other AITS working in the project.

